

An Analysis of Employment Issues for Sports Science Graduates

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Yazar Katkı Oranı:

- A) Çalışmanın Tasarımı
- B) Veri Toplama
- C) Verilerin Analizi
- D) Makale Yazımı
- E) Eleştirel Okuma

ABSTRACT

This study aims to examine the employment policies of the Ministry of Youth and Sports with a focus on the priority given to graduates of Sports Sciences, within the framework of the personnel recruitment announcement issued in 2023 and the dimensions of the Decree-Law No. 638 on the Organization of the Ministry of Youth and Sports and the National Youth and Sports Policy Document. This study was conducted using a qualitative research model and document analysis design. The research involved a thematic analysis of data obtained from academic journals, official reports, policy documents, and news sources, and a document analysis of the Ministry's announcement was performed and compared with the existing literature. According to the findings, the announcement for 1071 positions by the Ministry of Youth and Sports includes quotas for various fields ranging from technology and informatics to arts and communication, from theology to social sciences. This diversity indicates that the Ministry adopts a comprehensive approach to various youth-related fields. The number of quotas allocated for Sports Sciences graduates (208) indicates a significant employment opportunity in this field. However, compared to other fields, this quota is not very high, suggesting that the Ministry places greater emphasis on employment in other areas. According to the Ministry's personnel recruitment announcement, 208 out of a total of 1071 positions (approximately 19.4%) are allocated to Sports Sciences graduates. However, it is debatable to what extent this ratio aligns with the general duties and areas of activity of the Ministry.

Keywords: Sports Sciences Graduates, Access to Government Careers, Ministry of Youth and Sports, Employment Policies.

Spor Bilimleri Mezunlarının İstihdam Problemi Üzerine Bir Analiz

ÖZET

Bu çalışma, Gençlik ve Spor Bakanlığı'nın istihdam politikalarını 2023 yılında ilan ettiği personel alım ilanı çerçevesi ve Bakanlığın, "638 sayılı Gençlik ve Spor Bakanlığının Teşkilat" Kanun Hükmünde Kararnamenin ve "Ulusal Gençlik ve Spor Politikası Belgesi" boyutlarını ele alarak, Spor Bilimleri mezunlarının önceliği odağında incelemeyi amaçlamaktadır. Bu çalışma, nitel araştırma modeli ve doküman analizi deseni kullanılarak gerçekleştirilmiştir. Araştırma kapsamında akademik dergiler, resmi raporlar, politika belgeleri ve haber kaynaklarından elde edilen veriler tematik bir yaklaşımla analiz edilerek Gençlik ve Spor Bakanlığının ilanı doküman analizi yapılarak mevcut literatürle karşılaştırılmıştır. Elde edilen bulgulara göre, Gençlik ve Spor Bakanlığının 1071 kişi için açtığı ilan, teknoloji ve bilişimden sanat ve iletişime, ilahiyattan, sosyal bilimlere kadar geniş bir yelpazede farklı uzmanlık alanlarına yönelik kontenjanlar içermektedir. Bu çeşitlilik, Bakanlığın gençlikle ilgili çeşitli alanlarda kapsamlı bir yaklaşım benimsediğini göstermektedir. Spor Bilimleri mezunları için ayrılan kontenjan sayısı (208), bu alanda ciddi bir istihdam fırsatı sunduğunu işaret ediyor. Ancak, bu kontenjan diğer alanlarla kıyaslandığında yüksek olmamakla birlikte, Bakanlığın diğer alanlardaki istihdama daha fazla önem verdiğini göstermektedir. Bakanlığın personel alım ilanına göre, toplam 1071 kişilik kontenjandan 208'i (yaklaşık %19,4) Spor Bilimleri mezunlarına ayrıldığı görülmektedir. Ancak, bu oranın Bakanlığın genel görev ve faaliyet alanlarına ne derece uygun olduğu tartışılabilir.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Spor Bilimleri Mezunları, Devlet Kariyerine Erişim, Gençlik ve Spor Bakanlığı, İstihdam Politikaları.

ISSN: 3023-5359

Doi Number:

Introduction

Employment is a critical issue that lies at the core of both economic and social policies, involving numerous disciplines. This field encompasses the total of individuals actively working or seeking employment in the labor market, serving as a fundamental parameter indicating the health and productivity of an economy. The multifaceted nature of employment has been explored in-depth through studies in various fields, such as economics, sociology, business, and law. These studies reveal that employment is not merely an economic term but an integral part of societal and individual life. This research aims to comprehensively examine the employment policies of the Ministry of Youth and Sports, considering all these dimensions. The Ministry's policies will be analyzed in the light of the aforementioned diverse disciplines. In this way, the study aims to understand the employment policies not only from an economic perspective but also from social and cultural dimensions.

Employment

Employment is a central issue in economic and social policies, engaging multiple disciplines. It refers to the field where individuals work in exchange for wages or salaries (Fougere et al., 2000). As an economic term, it denotes the total number of individuals in the labor market (Malcomson, 1999). Employment is a significant indicator of the health and efficiency of an economy. Studies in fields such as economics, sociology, business, and law have highlighted the complex structure of employment (Rhodes, 2015).

Employment from an Economic Perspective

In economic literature, employment refers to the condition of individuals working in exchange for wages (Hoffman, 1979). Keynesian economic theories argue that macroeconomic policies can regulate unemployment and employment, while neoclassical approaches suggest that market mechanisms and individual choices will regulate the labor market. Employment

policies are directly related to economic growth, unemployment rates, inflation, and wages (Crompton, 2010).

Employment from a Sociological and Demographic Perspective

Sociological studies examine the social structure and demographic impacts of employment. Variables such as gender, age, ethnic origin, and educational level and their effects on employment are frequently discussed in this field (Pagano & Pica, 2012). For example, the participation rates of women in the workforce, the role of the elderly in employment, and youth unemployment are central topics in sociological research (Godard, 2014).

Employment from a Business and Management Perspective

In business literature, human resource management, the implementation of employment policies, and workforce productivity are important topics (Domar, 1947). Employer branding, employee satisfaction, and organizational commitment play critical roles in gaining competitive advantages for businesses. Furthermore, topics such as employee training and development, workforce planning, and performance management are frequently discussed in this field (Hipple, 2010).

Employment in a Legal Framework

Employment law includes legal rules and standards that regulate labor relations. Issues such as employment contracts, working hours, wages, occupational health and safety, union rights, and dismissal are fundamental components of employment law (Hoffman, 2010). These legal frameworks, which vary at national and international levels, play an important role in protecting employee rights and defining employer obligations (Ford, 2014).

The Impacts of Globalization and Technological Advancements on Employment

Globalization and technological advancements are factors that deeply affect employment markets (Cirillo, 2017). Phenomena such as global competition,

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workforce mobility, and remote working have changed the structure of employment markets and labor demand. Technological advancements, including automation and artificial intelligence, have led to the disappearance of some professions and the creation of new job areas (Aghion et al., 2019).

Types of Employment

- *Full-Time Employment:* Employment where individuals work on specific days of the week, usually covering standard daily working hours.
- *Part-Time Employment:* Employment where individuals work fewer hours per week and generally have flexible working hours.
- *Temporary Employment:* Employment that is valid for a specific period or project and usually has a specific end date.
- *Freelance Employment:* Employment where individuals work independently, often making short-term or project-based agreements with multiple employers.
- *Remote (Home-Based) Work:* Work performed outside of the workplace, usually from home, with the aid of technology (Sema, 2012; Özen, 2015; Pissarides, 2001).

Employment Policies

Employment policies include strategies and methods developed by governments to regulate the labor market and protect workers' rights (Fougere et al., 2000). These policies aim to reduce unemployment rates, enhance job security, and increase the efficiency of the job market (Selamoğlu, 2002). Additionally, these policies are shaped in accordance with economic theories, social needs, and political goals. Employment policies are addressed differently by Keynesian and neoclassical economic theories. The Keynesian approach emphasizes government intervention and public spending to reduce unemployment and increase employment (Avendano & Berkman, 2014). In contrast, the neoclassical approach

gives more weight to market mechanisms and individual choices. These two theories represent different economic understandings at the foundation of employment policies (Calmfors & Nymoer, 1990).

Employment policies are often divided into "active" and "passive" categories. Active employment policies include direct interventions such as improving the efficiency of the labor market, placing unemployed individuals into work, and providing vocational training. Passive employment policies encompass support mechanisms designed to cope with unemployment, such as unemployment insurance and social benefits (Han et al., 2009).

Globalization and technological developments have led to the reshaping of employment policies (Sonnet et al., 2014). In particular, digitalization and automation have changed the structure of the job market, necessitating new policy approaches. In this context, the development of digital skills, adaptation to innovative business models, and flexible working arrangements have become important (Ağpak & Özçiçek, 2018).

Employment policies are also examined from perspectives of social justice and equality. Factors such as gender, age, ethnicity, and disability are critical in ensuring equal opportunities in the job market. In this regard, special employment programs for disadvantaged groups and anti-discrimination laws have been developed (Sonnet et al., 2014).

Employment policies are an evolving field within the context of economic theories, global trends, and social needs. Employment is a dynamic and multidimensional issue that needs to be addressed from economic, sociological, business, legal, and technological perspectives (Jochem, 2011). This diversity presents different challenges and opportunities for policymakers, employers, and workers. Effective design and implementation of employment policies are key to sustainable economic growth and social welfare. The development of effective employment policies is crucial not only for

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economic growth and stability but also for social justice and equality (Storey, 1995).

Employment Policies of the Ministry of Youth and Sports

In 2023, the Ministry of Youth and Sports announced vacancies in the 'Information and Technology Sector (Group 1): Required Education: Information Systems and Technologies, Computer Sciences, Computer Engineering, etc., with a quota of 171 positions. Art and Communication Sector (Group 2): Required Education: Fields related to art, such as Painting, Music, Photography, and areas like Communication Sciences, New Media and Communication, with a quota of 199 positions. Sports Sciences Sector (Group 3): Required Education: Coaching Education, Sports Management, Recreation, Exercise and Sports Sciences, etc., with a quota of 208 positions. Social Sciences Sector (Group 4): Required Education: Sociology, Psychology, Social Work, Theology, etc., with a quota of 205 positions. General Group (Group 5): Required Education: Any undergraduate program, with a quota of 248 positions. Youth Leadership (Group 6): Required Education: Completion of the Youth Leadership Training provided by the Ministry of Youth and Sports, regardless of degree field, with a quota of 40 positions" (Ministry of Youth and Sports, 2023).

The 'National Youth and Sports Policy Document' (Official Gazette, 2013), under the heading 'Legal Basis,' states: 'The National Youth and Sports Policy Document is prepared by the Ministry and submitted for approval to the Council of Ministers to ensure coordination and cooperation among public institutions and organizations that directly or indirectly influence youth and sports policies, and it is revised and updated at least every four years. In updating the National Youth and Sports Policy Document, suggestions from relevant public institutions and organizations, sports federations, and NGOs are considered' (Ministry of Youth and Sports, 2013).

In conclusion, while forming its personnel employment policies, the Ministry prioritizes

sports as well as values related to youth. Consequently, it is evident that the personnel recruitment policies are developed based on youth activities. This explains why the employment rates in the 2023 personnel announcement for graduates from Sports Sciences are approximately 19.4%.

Looking at advanced countries in sports, for example, the employment policy of the Ministry of Sports in the United Kingdom has developed a strategy titled "Get Active: a strategy for the future of sport and physical activity" (GOV.UK., 2023). This strategy focuses on increasing sports participation and physical activity levels in the UK. Main goals include physical and mental health, individual development, social and community development, and economic growth. Additionally, making sports and physical activities more inclusive and accessible to everyone, and making the sector more sustainable and financially resilient, are among the fundamental components of this strategy. In the UK, employment in the field of Youth and Sports is implemented in a more open and sustainable manner (UK Sport, 2024). Ultimately, employment conducted via public internet access demonstrates transparency and sustainability, and focuses on sports sciences.

When comparing the approaches to personnel employment in the field of Youth and Sports between the two countries;

Turkey: Specifies quotas for various disciplines targeting specific expertise areas, attempting to meet the diverse needs in the field of Youth and Sports. This is evident in the ministry's announcement, which prioritizes the need for personnel to support various youth-related activities outside of sports activities, as seen in the "Social Sciences Sector (Group 4): Required Education: Sociology, Psychology, Social Work, Theology, etc., with a quota of 205 positions" (Ministry of Youth and Sports, 2023).

United Kingdom: Aims within a general strategy framework to make sports and physical activity accessible and sustainable

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for all sections of society. This approach is built on increasing sports participation and expanding the positive effects of sports on society, prioritizing transparency and public access to current personnel employment resources, and facilitating accessibility through "<https://www.uk sport.gov.uk/jobs>" (GOV.UK, 2023).

In conclusion, the Ministries of Youth and Sports in Turkey and the United Kingdom adopt different employment policies in line with their own needs and goals. Turkey's approach specifies quotas for various disciplines targeting specific expertise areas to meet the diverse needs in the field of Youth and Sports, while the UK focuses on general sports participation and spreading physical activity across the general population. This clearly demonstrates the different emphases and approaches in the sports and youth policies of both countries, highlighting the significance of these differences in terms of demonstrating the distinct emphases and approaches in the sports and youth policies of both nations.

Methods

The primary aim of this research is to compile existing literature on employment and to evaluate the policies of the Ministry of Youth and Sports within this context. The literature review section of the article includes a comprehensive survey of sources analyzing employment from economic, sociological, business, legal, and technological perspectives. Academic journals, official reports, policy documents, and current news sources have been utilized for this purpose. Furthermore, the official websites of the Ministry of Youth and Sports and the UK's Ministry of Sport, along with their published announcements and policy documents, have been thoroughly examined.

Data Analysis

The announcement of the Ministry of Youth and Sports was analyzed through document analysis and compared with the existing literature. The collected literature was examined using a thematic approach.

Thematic analysis is the process of identifying, analyzing, and reporting patterns (themes) within data. This method allows for a rich and detailed understanding of the data while addressing research questions. Thematic analysis enables the grouping of data into meaningful categories and the examination of the relationships between these categories. This method helps researchers gain a deep understanding of the data and provide comprehensive explanations about specific phenomena (Braun & Clarke, 2006). The connections between the theoretical foundations, policies, and practices of employment in different disciplines were analyzed. The employment policies of the Ministry of Youth and Sports were evaluated comparatively with the existing literature.

Methodological Approach

This study adopts a qualitative research approach. It aims to provide a new understanding and perspective by compiling and analyzing existing information. The existing data and information in the literature have been used to answer research questions and to facilitate a broader understanding of employment policies.

Ethical Evaluation

All data and sources used in the study have been cited in accordance with academic ethical standards. During the research process, copyright and intellectual property rights have been respected, ensuring the correct and fair use of sources.

Conclusion

The Ministry of Youth and Sports' 2023 announcement for 1,071 positions spans a wide range of expertise areas from technology and informatics to art and communication, from theology to social sciences. This diversity demonstrates the Ministry's comprehensive approach to youth-related fields. The quota set aside for graduates in Sports Sciences has been determined to be 208, providing significant employment opportunities in the Sports Sciences area. However, this quota is relatively low compared to other areas, indicating that the Ministry places greater importance on other fields of employment.

According to the Ministry's 2023 personnel recruitment announcement, 208 out of the total quota of 1,071 positions (approximately 19.4%) are allocated to graduates in Sports Sciences. Although this is considered a significant quota for the 'Sports Sciences' group within the Ministry, the appropriateness of this rate in relation to the Ministry's overall mission and activities may be debated.

Among the Ministry's core tasks are promoting youth and sports activities, developing sports science and education, managing sports facilities, and protecting athletes' health. In this context, while the representation of 'Sports Sciences' graduates within the Ministry should be a priority, prioritizing other groups in the announcement provides insight into the Ministry's employment policy priorities.

Furthermore, the quotas allocated in other groups (such as informatics, art and communication, social sciences, and theology) demonstrate the Ministry's priority to serve other youth-related activity areas. This diversity shows the Ministry's comprehensive approach in various youth-related fields. The development and support of artistic, cultural, educational, and technological programs targeted at youth are also important. Therefore, when evaluating whether the quota allocated to Sports Sciences graduates is fair, the comprehensive nature of

the Ministry's overall goals and activities must also be considered.

In conclusion, while the quota of 208 positions allocated for Sports Sciences graduates offers significant employment opportunities in this field, it constitutes a relatively low rate compared to other areas. The quota rate allocated to Sports Sciences graduates serves the Ministry's needs in the sports field, but it may be balanced according to the Ministry's other activity areas and objectives. In addition to the Ministry's overall missions and objectives, the challenges and needs encountered in the field of youth and sports may also have influenced the distribution of quotas.

Conflict of Interest Declaration

There are no potential conflicts of interest related to the research, authorship, and publication of this article.

Support/Funding Information

The author has not received any financial support for the research, authorship, and/or publication of this article.

Ethics Committee Decision

There is no need for an ethics committee to make decisions for this research.

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